

Supplemental Figure 1. Nonreplicating *Toxoplasma gondii* uracil auxotroph CPS-invaded myeloid cells are present in the PLN, pancreas, omentum, and peritoneum. Pan02 tumors were established in mice for 14 days. 14 days after tumor challenge, Pan02 tumor-bearing mice were intraperitoneally vaccinated with cell-trace violet labeled CPS uracil auxotrophs ($n = 4$), or were intraperitoneally injected with PBS ($n = 4$). Cells isolated from peritoneum (P), omentum (O), pancreatic lymph node (PLN) and pancreas (Panc) were analyzed 24 hours to determine the percentage of CPS-invaded CD45⁺CD11b⁺CD11c⁺F4/80⁻ dendritic cells (A) and CPS-invaded CD45⁺CD11b⁺CD11c⁺F4/80⁺Gr-1⁻ macrophage populations (B).

Supplementary Figure 2. Representative FACS plots are shown for the different tissues. See Supplementary Figure 1 for experimental details.